

The Whispers

A Journal of Tribal Life, Literatures and Cultures

Published by Sanskruti Kendra, Sundargarh, Odisha, India

Volume I, Issue I, August 2024

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13854850

From the Editor

The power of human voice is perhaps greater than that of an explosive in content and effect because the latter may affect a place at a given time, but the former runs across time and space endlessly not without producing results. Several people, including foreigners and non-tribal Indians, have spoken and written on and for the tribal community trying to bring them to the public notice and to raise them from their plight, but all these years the voice from the tribal people themselves was not much to be heard anywhere apart from their own closed circle. The result is that just as the tribal community is physically hidden in the sylvan trove, so also its reality and voice is hidden from the populace of the world.

The tribal are vocal telling or singing their content in the air of the fields and forests for their own joy and satisfaction and that of the community, but nothing was recorded or documented that would stand the test of time and be visible to the people. That is why there exists virtually nothing in the libraries and archives of the literate world. Today, as time advances in the sapient path with stacks of documents on all available subjects, all want to have a look at the documented tribal language, literature, society and culture; but that is where the tribal society goes blank.

A long wait, however, comes to an end as the first edition of 'THE WHISPERS: A JOURNAL FOR TRIBAL LIFE, SOCIETY AND CULTURES' comes to light breaking the monotony of silence from the part of the tribal themselves. It is a joy for all of us to see some tribals coming out as a body with the fruit of their intellect for their benefit and the benefit of the community. A humble initiative always goes a long way to create a beginning that might run across time and eventually manifest stability and greatness. And indeed, that is what we all are hoping and trying for in this effort to bring out the journal.

It may have already gone to our notice that the 'THE WHISPERS' is a multi-lingual and multi-dimensional journal. It includes research works, creative writings, narratives and critiques written in not less than nine languages – English, Hindi, Odia, Sadri, Oraon, Munda, Kisan, Kharia and Kenta, and in three scripts – English, Hindi and Odia. What greater platform than this would our educated

intellectuals need to come out with their intellectual, creative and critical efforts? It is only a matter of will and a little effort to bring out something in the form of writing because nothing comes out of anyone without as much as a minimum of this.

We know we have taken quite some time, even after collecting the materials, to finalise the form of the Journal and register it for our proper identity and authenticity. But this is an unavoidable part of the effort, and we hope to be regular in our further issues. The Journal is expected to be biannual viz. coming out twice a year, depending on our regularity in providing matters for publication. I appeal to all educated individuals and intellectuals to come out with any form of writing in any language and script as mentioned above. We must know and realise that writings in our own language will, with time, be a big deposit of literature or intellectual works for our posterity to learn and enjoy.

Fr. Dr. Ignatius Soreng SVD, Ph.D.

Chief Editor

21.08.2024
